

OSF Use Case: Pattern Glare sensitivity distinguishes subclinical autism and schizotypy

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Tell us more about the research study that generated this dataset. Please briefly describe the data that was shared or reused.

This study behaviorally identified early visual processing differences between non-clinical individuals with autism-like traits and those with schizotypy traits. Schizophrenia and autism symptoms substantially overlap clinically, which heightens risk of misdiagnosis. However, patients with autism and schizophrenia tend to elicit divergent sensory cortical profiles. Those with schizophrenia tend to be hypo-excitabile (under-respond to sensory information) while those with autism tend to be hyperexcitable (over-respond to sensory information). With this dataset, we analyzed a behavioral correlate of visual hyperexcitability in adults exhibiting sub-clinical traits of ASD and SZ to identify potential differences in sensory processing in the absence of clinical confounds.

We used the Pattern Glare Test (PGT), an achromatic high contrast mid-range spatial frequency grating pattern that participants view for five seconds before

reporting any illusions they saw in the pattern. Visually sensitive individuals report more illusions from the PGT, which has been linked with cortical hyperexcitability. The visual system over-responds to such patterns with potential to cause discomfort, headaches, and seizures in patients with photosensitive epilepsy. The over-excitation is theorized to stimulate neighboring areas of the cortex producing the illusions. This makes the PGT a robust behavioral measure of cortical excitability without having to ask about symptoms of visual sensitivity or discomfort.

The dataset contains PGT responses, Schizotypal Personality Questionnaire - Brief Revised (SPQ-BR) scores, Autism Quotient (AQ) scores, and brief demographic information. All factor data for the SPQ-BR and AQ are available in the dataset.

How would you describe the potential impact of this work to someone outside of your field?

For basic scientists, our work can inform researchers interested in understanding factors that affect or are affected by vision or visual cortical hyperexcitability. Our findings echo prior reporting on the effects of mid-frequency gratings on visually sensitive individuals, which may inform future product development aimed at reducing visual discomfort.

For clinical scientists and clinicians, our work underscores subclinical symptoms linked to cortical disruptions that may inform efforts for early identification.

How could your findings be used in future research?

Our findings can be used to further explore neural and behavioral differences between schizophrenia and autism at clinical and subclinical levels, as well as research assessing the effect of visual sensitivity/cortical excitability on symptoms and cognition in clinical and subclinical individuals.

How has data sharing evolved over the past decade in your field? What advice do you have for other researchers about sharing/reusing data?

Previously, trying to share data required working out common software and gaining access to servers to transfer and manipulate files. This led to security concerns and wasted time waiting for access to data. Now, having places like OSF as conduits to provide secure access to data on lots of different platforms eliminates the concern.

Sometimes there are good reasons for not sharing data, particularly if de-identifying data is impossible. However, excuses regarding lost data, lack of organization, or no secure way of transferring data are now not acceptable and can be in violation of funding agreements. This has resulted in the likelihood of getting the data significantly increasing. Second, making data accessible requires documentation and organization. We've been using this as a great excuse to spend time backing up final projects. We now find it much easier to go back to previous projects and identify details that were missed in the

papers, reuse code, or reanalyze data from years ago. In terms of advice, we recommend taking the time to document your project, make your data accessible, and make your materials as user-friendly as possible. Future you will be thankful you did. We frequently recommend OSF to other researchers who intend to share or reuse data because we find the process user-friendly and the repository reputable.

Where else have you shared data or found data to reuse? How easy/difficult did you find using OSF?

While funded by the National Institute of Mental Health, we shared data with the National Data Archive. We've also shared data and materials using GitHub, FigShare, and medRxiv. We've downloaded data from ABIDE II, NITRC, and the Human Connectome Project.

Sharing data through OSF is more convenient, simple, and streamlined than other repositories we've used. OSF's data storing system is easy to use and provides an intuitive organizational structure. Plus, OSF allows access via other applications including GitHub, Box, FigShare, etc. Researchers interested in data from a project can access information about the study along with corresponding data, author information, and sometimes even a preprint. This improves transparency, increases communication between scientists, and maintains the opportunity to reuse/reanalyze data for new exploration.

For scientists sharing data, including further information and facilitating communication and acquisition increases

scientific integrity and transparency. In addition, this process preserves the project for the long-term.

How can the data repository landscape evolve to better support data sharing and reuse?

The data repository landscape could be improved by including descriptors to data type (survey behavioral vs. behavioral task) per project to increase data discovery. For large datasets, cost-effective data storage methods would also be helpful, particularly if institutional access fluctuates.

Why is it important that your data be made publicly available?

Scientific progress is often born from collaboration and authentic data. We share on OSF first to increase data transparency. Second, to facilitate access to data, which helps scientific progress and visibility. Third, it is required/expected by our funding agency (although we would anyway.)

How has sharing your data impacted your research or collaborations?

A researcher recently reached out requesting further information with the intention to use our data in their work. Sharing data has harbored a culture of accountability by pushing us as researchers to have well-documented and readable code, as well as easy-to-use ReadMe files, etc. It has also facilitated new connections and collaborations across the globe. Now we can connect directly over a dataset.